

Framing Industrial City Icons: Cross-Media Analysis of Post-War Urban Iconization with the CLARIAH Media Suite

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This contribution presents the setup of the CLARIAH Research Fellowship project ‘Framing Industrial City Icons (FICI): Cross-Media Analysis of Post-War Urban Iconization’, and research conducted in its context. The FICI project centers on the question: how have landmarks of Dutch industrial cities been framed as icons, both visually and discursively, in national media during the post-war period? It operationalizes a cross-media analysis of post-war urban iconization processes, on the basis of different Dutch cultural heritage and media collections within the digital research environment of the CLARIAH Media Suite.

The project starts from the consideration that studies of urban icons - here defined as recognizable landmarks that embody cities’ (aspired) identities - have mostly prioritized contemporary and global research frameworks (Ethington and Schwartz 2006), and thereby forgone investigations of local embeddedness, across historical time frames, and pinpointed to particular types of cities (Low 1996). Industrial cities, specifically, have frequently boasted prominent architecture and infrastructure linked to local workers’ culture and society (Sennema and Van de Laar 2021). Prior to World War II, avant-garde artists for instance played an important role in representing and promoting modern industrial landmarks (Paalman 2011; Van Veen 2019), while the mid-1990s heralded a new emphasis on cultural significance and ‘starchitecture’ that even has led some scholars to announce the fall or increasing predictability of icons in urban landscapes nowadays (Kaika 2011). The post-war period, however, remains rather underexplored in this respect. To fill this research gap, while building on recent Dutch literature (Verheul 2012; Bayer et al. 2015), three landmarks from different Dutch industrial cities and with historical overlap are investigated as case studies in this project, namely: Tilburg’s TextielMuseum (opened in 1958), located in former factory buildings; Rotterdam’s Euromast (°1960), erected around the time that the port became world leader; and Eindhoven’s Evoluon (°1966), built as tribute to Philips’ history. This conference contribution will mostly highlight the Euromast and Evoluon cases, due to their similar nature as modernist and purpose-built urban landmarks.

Starting from the general understanding of ‘icon’ as ‘something regarded as a representative symbol or as worthy of veneration’ (Oxford English Dictionary), the FICI project builds upon and scrutinizes the word ‘frame’ in a double way, namely: framing something visually, by filming or photographing it in certain ways; and framing something discursively, by talking or writing about it in certain ways. This motivates the project’s use of different media collections in the CLARIAH Media Suite - most importantly the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision’s television and radio collections, and at a later stage also the Royal Library of the Netherlands’ newspaper collection - and related tools to annotate and analyze cultural sources on the aforementioned urban industrial icons, in order to investigate how processes of iconization have manifested themselves through different media and potentially evolved over time. On a more general level, the project’s goal is ultimately to identify recurring visual and discursive tropes across historical media collections, and in doing so also to outline new workflows and recommendations for multimodal annotation and analysis. Television and radio material forms the main focus of the presented project, as

newspaper material is only being considered at a later stage, in part due to these sources' partial integration in the CLARIAH Media Suite at the moment.

This contribution will reflect on the application of systematic annotation codes across media items' visual (shot type, camera movement) and discursive (word type, rhetorical device) characteristics in television and radio collections. On the basis of key characteristics ascribed to urban icons (Ethington and Schwartz 2006), this contribution presents the following hypotheses, to reflect on through its case studies and to stimulate recommendations on cross-media annotation work within the CLARIAH Media Suite environment: 1) urban icons' function as ultimate representations of particular cities translates itself in a variety of visual and discursive framing methods during their earlier, event-oriented life stages; 2) later life stages of urban icons are characterized by an increasing homogenization or consistency across media representations; 3) as urban icons develop into dominant cultural clichés of particular cities, their media representations become more timeless or, in contrast, rather tend to emphasize their obsolescence and anachronistic character.

References

- Bayer, Marcel, et al. *Terug naar de fabriek: 25 industriële iconen met nieuwe energie*. Amsterdam: Oostenwind, 2015.
- Ethington, Philip J., and Vanessa R. Schwartz. "Introduction: An Atlas of the Urban Icons Project." *Urban History* 33.1 (2006): 5-19.
- Kaika, Maria. "Autistic Architecture: The Fall of the Icon and the Rise of the Serial Object of Architecture." *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space* 29.6 (2011): 968-92.
- Low, Setha M. "The Anthropology of Cities: Imagining and Theorizing the City." *Annual Review of Anthropology* 25 (1996): 383-409.
- Paalman, Floris. *Cinematic Rotterdam: The Times and Tides of a Modern City*. Rotterdam: 010 Publishers, 2011.
- Sennema, Hilde, and Paul van de Laar. "Rotterdam's New Waterway: The Iconification of an Infrastructure (1860-1947)." *European Journal of Creative Practices in Cities and Landscapes* 4.1 (2021): 77-94.
- Van Veen, Anneke. *Modern Perspectives: Foto en Film Amsterdam 1920-1940*. Bussum: Uitgeverij THOTH, 2019.
- Verheul, Wouter Jan. *Stedelijke iconen: Het ontstaan van beeldbepalende projecten tussen betoog en beton*. The Hague: Boom Lemma Uitgevers, 2012.